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Optimization of federated learning topology in Internet of Things
ecosystems

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Abstract

Optimization of federated learning topology in Internet of Things ecosystems

Concerns about preserving the privacy of data used in Machine Learning have been rising steadily for the last couple of years. Similarly, a big focus in current research is decreasing the amount of energy needed for training a state-of-the-art model due to the significant carbon footprint of current data centers. Meanwhile, the number of smart appliances that have substantial computational capabilities and connections to robust Internet of Things infrastructures, and yet are not meaningfully engaging these resources is only growing. Federated learning, a paradigm that proposes training the model on a federation of clients with a central server aggregating the updates, has the chance to mitigate both of these concerns by leveraging the full capabilities of IoT devices. However, for it to happen, stable solutions providing a reliable, efficient and convergent Internet of Things implementation of federated learning have to be developed. This study will focus on testing and evaluating the performance of various topologies against specific limitations of edge computing environments. To do so, a set of system components providing the functionalities of federated learning clients and server was implemented. It was then used for testing and analysis of various topologies.

Keywords: Internet of Things, federated learning, computing on edge, topology

Streszczenie

Optymalizacja topologii uczenia federowanego w ekosystemach Internetu Rzeczy

Wątpliwości dotyczące zachowania prywatności danych wykorzystywanych w procesie uczenia maszynowego narastają przez ostatnie lata. Podobnie, znaczną uwagę w obecnych badaniach zwraca się na zmniejszenie ilości energii potrzebnej do treningu modeli zgodnych z aktualnym stanem wiedzy ze względu na istotny ślad węglowy generowany przez współczesne centra danych. Tymczasem liczba inteligentnych urządzeń połączonych z rozbudowanymi infrastrukturami Internetu Rzeczy o istotnych, niewykorzystanych możliwościach obliczeniowych sukcesywnie rośnie. Uczenie federowane, paradygmat proponujący trenowanie modelu za pomocą federacji klientów z centralnym serwerem agregującym aktualizacje wag, może stanowić część rozwiązania obu tych problemów poprzez wykorzystanie pełnego potencjału takich urządzeń. Żeby jednak tak się stało, muszą powstać stabilne rozwiązania problemu niezawodnej, wydajnej i zbieżnej implementacji uczenia federowanego w ekosystemie Internetu Rzeczy. Głównym celem tej pracy jest zidentyfikowanie i stworzenie najbardziej optymalnych topologii dla ograniczeń przetwarzania brzegowego. Z tego powodu został zaimplementowany zestaw komponentów zapewniających funkcjonalności klientów i serwerów w systemie uczenia federowanego. Ten zestaw był następnie użyty do analizy i testowania różnych topologii.

Słowa kluczowe: Internet Rzeczy, uczenie federowane, przetwarzanie brzegowe, topologia

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Oświadczenie

Oświadczam, że pracę magisterską pod tytułem „Optimization of federated learning topology in Internet of Things ecosystems” której promotorem jest dr inż. Karolina Wasielewska-Michniewska, wykonałam samodzielnie, co poświadczam własnoręcznym podpisem.

Karolina Bogacka

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Introduction

One of the critical bottlenecks of machine learning development lies in the ability to collect, process and use large amounts of data. However, this data is often stored locally and hard to access due to a multitude of reasons, which is a problem especially for the development of novel, less well-known features. When image recognition is already trained on large, open-source datasets, many problems have little to no access to similar datasets in their domains (Roh, Heo, and Whang 2021). Firstly, there are ongoing controversies concerning the collection and safe storage of information (Murdoch 2021). Many impressive developments in Deep Learning, especially concerning services available on mobile applications, rely on the model periodically being retrained on, often private, data. This data, frequently containing type history or visited locations, can be considered sensitive. Hosting it in a centralized location, even in adherence to strict legislation, still poses a large security risk, and leads to repeating scandals and data leaks (Zheng, Hu, and Han 2020),(Mothukuri et al. 2021),(Lu et al. 2020).

Moreover, many of the latest advancements in Deep Learning involve the creation of highly complex "state of the art" models, which require a substantial amount of computational resources and power (Hu et al. 2021). This increases the cost, and with that, the carbon footprint of training. As for now, the yearly energy consumption of the data centers enabling Deep Learning research represents 0.3% of global CO_2 emissions. A substantial number, compared to the 2% emitted by the entire information and communications technology ecosystem, which is expected to grow even bigger (Qiu et al. 2021). Recent advancements suggest solutions employing edge computing, for example micro data centers, could be considered a viable alternative (Bilal et al. 2018).

However, federated learning architectures, consisting often of a large set of heterogenous edge devices, need to be robust towards particular challenges it may bring, such as the issues with latency, suddenly dropped or renewed connections with clients, client computational constraints or local data distributions not being representative of the problem (Tak and Cherkaoui 2021), (Khan et al. 2020b). In those cases, centralized approach may not always be the most appropriate one, due to it having significant communication overhead and a single point of failure (Chou et al. 2021). On the other hand, fully decentralized topologies can still involve a significant

communication cost, just not limited to node-to-server communication (Jiang et al. 2020). It is worth mentioning that existing architectures tend to combine these paradigms in order to additionally improve convergence bound and scalability, for example by combining decentralized groups with a centralized update schema (Lee et al. 2020).

Additionally, for a meaningful reduction of energy in comparison with data centers it is important to minimize the energy consumption stemming from communication, as well as achieve cases of fast model convergence, which might be delayed by previously mentioned issues (Qiu et al. 2021). Therefore it would be beneficial to outline a form of component organisation as resistant to them as possible. In other words, it is important to investigate the most apt topology for this system.

1. Task formulation and state-of-the-art

1.1. Task description

Federated learning as a paradigm promises both training without centralized storage of data, as well as decreased carbon footprint by utilisation of many existing edge devices instead of a few large data centers. It has already been applied to a multitude of problems, from medical to IoT, transportation, defense and mobile apps (Aledhari et al. 2020). However, for it to become a common solution, further research concerning optimization will be necessary.

Topology here is understood as a network service topology represented by graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is a set of network functions, clients and server, and E corresponds to a set of connections between the functions (Fulber-Garcia et al. 2020).

This work aims to explore ways to construct a stable and efficient federated learning system, focusing specifically on its topology. Some research concerning the impact of topology on the performance of such systems has already been conducted, with proposals ranging from introducing sparsely connected cliques (Bellet, Kermarrec, and Lavoie 2021) to ring-based groups (Lee et al. 2020) to decentralized approaches (Hu, Jiang, and Wang 2019). The main goal of this study is further analysis of the proposed topology solutions and an attempt to unify and develop them, with special care shown to adapting to conditions specific to edge computing. In order to measure the performance of a specific experiment configuration, evaluation is carried out throughout the process of training (in the form of metrics such as aggregated loss and aggregated accuracy), as well as on the resulting model using the global test set (in the form of recall, precision, F1 measure and accuracy). This data is later compared between topologies.

1.2. Federated learning

Federated learning as a concept can be traced back to a 2016 paper developed by Google (McMahan et al. 2016), which also outlines basic challenges and aspirations of the field. The name for the approach came from the main idea, that the task is to be solved by a flexible

federation of collaborating devices, known also as clients, synchronized by a central server. The clients train the model using local data and send updates to the server, which later aggregates them and applies the results to the global model (Nguyen et al. 2021). In consequence, private data never leaves the clients (Kumar et al. 2021). Additionally, they can freely withdraw from the process.

Figure 1.1: Example of a centralized federated learning topology

Federated Optimization, consequently, refers to a setting for distributed optimization, in which data informing the problem is unevenly dispersed over a very large number of nodes, with each having the access only to a small fraction of data, which is additionally not representative of the global distribution. Still, the goal remains to train a well-performing centralized model. It is very important to prioritize communication efficiency in this setting. The very general objective of Federated Optimization, which describes the implicit optimization problem present in federated learning, can be specified as (Konečný, McMahan, and Ramage 2015):

$$\min_{w \in R^d} f(w) \quad \text{where } f(w) = 1/n \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(w).$$

Usually, the functions f_i are formulated with the use of a loss function l dependent on a pair of input-output data points x_i, y_i , $f_i(w) = l(w; x_i, y_i)$ (ibid.). The goal is to minimize the global loss function.

1.2. FEDERATED LEARNING

Three key challenges of the Federated Optimization problem can be formulated (McMahan et al. 2016):

- The training data on the clients is typically not independent and identically distributed, that is, not representative of the global distribution. In this case, the gradients gathered from the client are more representative of the local distribution than the global distribution, which results in a more biased averaged gradient. As a consequence, the training tends to be slow to converge. This causes problems mostly when combined with an effort to reduce communication, and therefore allowing the participant to perform multiple local updates (Bellet, Kermarrec, and Lavoie 2021).
- The size of the training data on the client varies significantly, which can also contribute to statistical heterogeneity of the system. As a result of all these factors, global model can underperform for local clients, which may disincentivize them towards participation in the process (Rahman et al. 2021).
- The number of clients active during training can be significantly larger than the average number of examples per client. Moreover, the average number of examples can be so small that local objectives greatly differ from global objectives and cause the model to fail. This is often the case for healthcare settings, but also more popular and successful domains, such as natural language processing or object detection (Kamp, Fischer, and Vreeken 2021).
- Employing far edge devices implies later problems with limited communication, stemming, for example, from issues related to clients suddenly exiting. These devices can be often large in numbers and connected to the server via unstable connections, which both increases the number of stragglers and the dropping probability of those with limited bandwidth. Both of the phenomena can further influence convergence (Bouacida et al. 2020).

As for update aggregation on the server, there are two families of algorithms employing different strategies to do so. The first one prioritizes generalization by acknowledging all layers and neurons of the local models. FedAvg, FedMA and FedProx belong to it. The second family emphasises client specialization and is represented, for example, by FedPer (Ek et al. 2021a).

As shown on Figure 1.2, for some specific usecases the choice of federated learning can lead to very good results, sometimes even surpassing models trained on the server. A very good example of this is one of the projects that introduced the concept of federated learning, namely a word prediction system used as a part of the Google keyboard system, Gboard.

Figure 1.2: A demonstration of the next word prediction system in Gboard. Based on the phrase "I love you", the system generates three viable word predictions. The model for word prediction in Gboard has been developed using federated learning, with the final top-1 and top-3 prediction impression recall being 1% higher in comparison with the server-trained solution (Hard et al. 2018). This photo was obtained by accessing Gboard from an iPhone 12 Pro Max set to Polish language in June 2022.

1.3. Internet of Things

Internet of Things (IoT), with its enhanced sensing and computing abilities, provides a broad range of devices, from smartphones to industrial cameras, with access to the Internet (Khan et al. 2020b). While it is now considered a broadly used term, there is no common definition of what it actually encompasses. The origins of it date back up to more than 20 years ago, to the work of the Auto-ID Labs at MIT on network radio-frequency identification infrastructures (Wortmann and Flüchter 2015). The International Telecommunication Union, however, defines it as “a set of related technologies that can be used together to achieve exciting ends, and it can be defined in terms of its contributing technologies, including the use of sensors, RFID chips, nanotechnologies and identification systems (chips, cards, SIMs), among others.” (Phillippa Biggs 2015). Federated

1.4. EDGE COMPUTING

learning will be very important in order to realize full intelligence in IoT systems at the network edge (Nguyen et al. 2021). However, combining federated learning with Internet of Things causes some issues, which must later be accounted for in Federated Optimization:

- The heterogeneity of the clients can cause delays produced by problems with latency or the presence of stragglers.
- The computing and storage resources on the far edge can be very limited, which impedes the use of large models. Additionally, the battery life of far edge devices pose restrictions on training time.
- The data used for the training can be highly redundant (Tak and Cherkaoui 2021).

1.4. Edge computing

It is a common practice today to store data and resources in remote cloud data centers, separated by a significant distance from the true sources of data in smartphones and wearables. Unfortunately, due to increased communication latency it is not a sustainable solution for large systems of devices. As a result, computing resources are often moved towards the edge of the network, physically closer to sensors and users (Hong and Varghese 2019). Those resources often take form of either micro data centers or augmented Internet nodes, and a computing model that employs them is called "edge computing" (Cao, Zhang, and Shi 2018). Alternatively, a model that combines edge and cloud computing can be referred to as "fog computing" (Skarlat et al. 2017). Edge computing, because of its concern with transmitting data closer to the edge and true location of user applications, is a promising area to be combined with federated learning. Coupled with a possible connection to a more abundant in resources server, this architecture results in a substantial reduction of latency in the system, since the data physically stays in the same area. Moreover, it leads to minimization of necessary bandwidth, because the user no longer relies on an overloaded central connection. This all can result in meaningful savings for the company that would decide to introduce such a solution (Xia et al. 2021). It is, however, important to acknowledge, that building an edge computing infrastructure involves its own set of necessary restrictions and rules (Khan et al. 2019):

- Mobility. The edge devices should be able to accommodate a moving end-user with no issues related to latency or bandwidth.
- Proximity. Edge devices should be positioned as close to the end users, as possible.

- Coverage. Network coverage must be far reaching.

These restrictions were later taken into consideration during the design of the basis for federated learning experiments in this work. Its clients would most probably consist of a large number of highly resource-constrained devices. Therefore those devices should communicate in a manner highly optimized towards low latency and efficient communication, and so, for example, have little direct connections to the remote server.

1.5. Related works

1.5.1. Recent developments in edge computing

According to (Guo et al. 2020), the dramatically increasing number of devices and data traffic in IoT architectures lead to a paradigm shift from centralized cloud computing to distributed edge computing. As such, multiple models have been proposed in order to replace the existing high-latency solutions, such as Cloudlets, which aim to bring a specific part of the cloud closer to mobile devices (Shaukat et al. 2016), fog computing, which provides low latency and ubiquitously available computation services by using easy to access micro computation access points (Bao et al. 2017) or mobile edge computing, which integrates computing, networking and storage resources with a base station on edge (Ahmed and Rehmani 2017). There is also ongoing research regarding edge cloud placement in the case of mobile computing in a way that would ensure optimal utilization of computation resources of each edge cloud, while providing real-time services and prioritizing user experience (Guo et al. 2020).

(Ren et al. 2020) additionally describes transparent computing as a possible way to decouple the software from the heterogenous hardware of IoT devices. To achieve this, transparent computing enables devices to choose services on demand via networks, with client devices being able to request them from the server side and later execute in a block-streaming manner. This model aims to reduce issues with the lack of resources on edge in heterogenous networks.

In order not to compromise the performance gain provided by edge computing and avoid issues related to limited spectrum resources, capacity-constrained batteries and context unawareness, more general research regarding optimization has also been conducted (Liao et al. 2020). More specifically here, it focused on channel selection as critical for reliable and efficient task delivery.

Some of the possible use cases to be realized in the future by edge computing might be the development of smart cities (Khan et al. 2020a). More concretely, a few motivational scenarios have been described in depth, such as the reporting of accidents involving autonomous cars,

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smart forest fire detection, smart home and smart parking systems. Recent advances involve improvements in smart transportation systems, such as advanced transport modes or traffic managements schemes, smart tourism enabled by augmented reality or even smart farming and healthcare.

As for practical solutions, a general-purpose networking framework prototype under the name Information-Centric edge (ICedge) has been developed (Mastorakis et al. 2020). It offers a fully distributed design with simulation and testbed results suggesting, that ICedge can achieve up to 50 times faster task completion compared to cases with no network-based compute reuse mechanisms.

1.5.2. Recent developments in federated learning

Federated learning is a very active and versatile area when it comes to research developments. For example, in the case of architecture, (Yang et al. 2019) defines two main types of it, horizontal federated learning and vertical federated learning, with the first being mostly used when the features between clients are similar, but data varies. Horizontal federated learning has been employed in medical cases, such as drug detection, or as an approach to modify Android mobile phone updates by Google (Aledhari et al. 2020). Vertical federated learning, on the other hand, combines data from clients with different feature and similar sample spaces (Liu et al. 2022). It provides unique to this federated learning paradigm benefits, such as the possibility of combining data from non-competing organizations in order to produce a better model, for example a bank, an insurance company and an e-commerce platform (Wei et al. 2022).

Another recently proposed architecture, here utilized for a very specific usecase, is called Federated Transfer Learning (Liu, Chen, and Yang 2018). Its main aim was to allow utilization of data from different sources in order to train the model. It obtained huge attention in healthcare industry (Jing et al. 2019).

(Cao et al. 2020) described a framework geared towards privacy preservation and parallel training. FEDF allows the model to be learned on a large number of geographically distributed training data sets, which could belong to different owners.

Not all optimization is done by optimizing architecture. There is also existing research focused on finding the best aggregating algorithm (with FedAvg winning so far) (Nilsson et al. 2018). Another proposed algorithmic solution, FedProx, is very similar to FedAvg, except it employs slight modifications that allow for even better performance and heterogeneity (Liu, Chen, and Yang 2018).

The choice of different optimization techniques can also be leveraged in order to optimize the

model, such as combining SGD with adaptive optimization methods (Adagrad, Yogi or Adam) in (Reddi et al. 2020), which resulted in an easier to tune federated learning system.

1.5.3. Topological proposals

Instead of focusing on optimizing a federated learning system through the improvement of aggregating algorithms, one could also focus on the network topology. Here, it is defined as the topological structure of the IoT network. Topology also refers to a mathematical concept concerned with the connectedness of objects in a graph (Anjum and Apsar Pasha 2015). The effect of topology on a heterogenous federated learning system is not well understood, but hard to deny (Bellet, Kermarrec, and Lavoie 2021). There have been a few different approaches to the optimization of it. Many of them focused on mitigating the issue of heterogeneity in federated learning data, often by properly grouping the nodes. (ibid.) presents D-Cliques, a topology that would aim to reduce gradient bias by grouping nodes in sparsely interconnected cliques such, that the label distribution in the clique would be representative of the global distribution. This approach led to convergence speed similar to that of a fully-connected topology with a 98% reduction in far edges and 96% reduction in the total number of messages. From a number of schemes tested with this approach, the fully-connected inter-clique scheme achieved the best convergence, with the small-world scheme closely following, the latter having significantly less far edges than the former. The fully-connected inter-clique scheme, however, still offers a significant reduction in the number of far edges compared to the classic approach, as well as increased robustness towards random far edge removal, which is an important observation in case of further development on edge.

A different perspective on dealing with divergence between data distribution on local client and the global distribution is described in (Ghosh et al. 2020). The work proposes an Iterative Federated Clustering Algorithm, which uses gradient descent to concurrently estimate the cluster affiliation of a client and train the appropriate model. As a result multiple models are obtained with performance optimized for the data distribution of the members of a specific cluster. A potential drawback of this technique is the increased training time and computation necessary, since the client evaluates multiple models in each iteration. These issues might be mitigated by modifications such as weight sharing and constraining cluster estimation to a few epochs.

Some approaches involved experiments with a star architecture and a ring architecture, as well as their combination. The reason behind it is to avoid the communication bottleneck present in the former while gaining the improved scalability and accuracy of the latter. More specifically, (Duan et al. 2021) focuses on a star architecture with ring-based groups, additionally describing

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an interesting self-balancing framework designed to mitigate the problem of a skewed global distribution, namely global class imbalance, in federated learning. While it offers substantial improvement in accuracy and communication traffic compared to Federated Averaging, its main objective is relatively narrow and does not involve concerns related to edge computing.

(Ding et al. 2020) outlines a ring architecture with star-based groups, assuming a realistic, while specific, usecase, in which unbalanced and non-i.i.d data has a periodically variational distribution. Leveraging this assumption in this case results in a linear speedup with respect to the number of clients. However, it also limits the usefulness of this method to instances that showcase those periodical properties in a substantial way.

(Eichner et al. 2019) mentions ring-based groups without global communication, also further elaborating on the periodically variational distribution of the data samples by leveraging it using semi-cyclic stochastic gradient descent. While it provides an important tool in dealing with heterogenous data, it's analysis concerned only the optimization of convex objectives using sequential SGD.

(Lee et al. 2020) investigates thoroughly the combination of star and ring architectures by proposing two forms of the TornadoAggregate algorithm: one with a ring architecture with star-based groups, the other with a star architecture with ring-based groups. The paper also outlines clear principles concerning reducing variance in a ring architecture. The results involve near-linear scalability and a substantially higher accuracy than the benchmark. Interestingly, it shows a substantial difference in results for the two architectures outlined in TornadoAggregate, with the version with star architecture and ring-based groups outperforming the ring architecture with star-based groups. This result might be attributed to the difference of communication interval for the two versions, with ring architecture having to take more steps for a group inter-node transfer.

(Mhaisen et al. 2022) describes a contrasting approach to data skewness mitigation in the form of a hierarchical federated learning system with Federated Gradient Descent being conducted on the user-edge layer and Federated Averaging between edges and the cloud. The resulting architecture is designed with an IoT environment in mind, with the potentially less efficient connections between edge and the server having to withstand much less frequent communication. The proposed heuristic for node allocation, however, was devised with a couple of strong assumptions in mind. Characteristics such as an equal amount of data per node or equal amount of nodes in various groups may not always be fulfilled by potential clients.

The paper of (Hu, Jiang, and Wang 2019) contains interesting ideas concerning IoT federated learning topology, such as the use of the segmentation to allow for large model training on

far edge. It is a vital suggestion due to the common decision of such works to assume large node-to-server bandwidths, which is a rare occurrence in IoT systems. The approach in (Hu, Jiang, and Wang 2019) relies on a combination of model segmentation level synchronization mechanisms, which divides the model into a set of not overlapping subsets, and a decentralized design reminiscent of the gossip protocol, with each worker randomly transferring the model segment to a few other workers. Model redundancy had to be included in order to ensure convergence. It is notable that the emergent prototype acknowledges the problem of workers suddenly exiting and returning. The results indeed reveal high convergence, but fail to thoroughly examine metrics such as accuracy. Additionally, this work presupposes a fully connected network along with data randomly distributed among clients.

This work has been further extended in (Jiang et al. 2020), forming a bandwidth-aware solution by greedily choosing a client with sufficient bandwidth to avoid delays. The convergence guarantees are also provided, with the training time being reduced up to 18 times compared to that of baselines with no accuracy degrade.

Another approach that leans into decentralized federated learning can be found in (Chen et al. 2021), there referred to as DAFCL. Every client is supposed to train the model based on its local data, and exchange the results with its neighbors through a symmetric and doubly stochastic matrix. The average model estimation is tracked throughout the process. Time-varying and sparse topology is the main focus, which makes it more suitable for an implementation using IoT. Nevertheless, an improvement in communication efficiency and additional robustness towards clients joining in or leaving during training without damaging the mixing matrix would be necessary.

(Li et al. 2021) offers an intriguing approach to the problem by presenting a blockchain-based federated learning framework with committee consensus. The mechanism of committee consensus was introduced in order to reduce malicious attacks and the amount of consensus computing. The blockchain here would be used for a global model storage, as well as exchanging local model updates. However, it needs large storage capacity on the client and would therefore be unsuitable for the edge. The system offers a solution, in which a portion of client can abandon historical blocks to release space, which would probably prove unsuitable for an environment with consistently limited resources. Nevertheless, it must be mentioned that approach provides substantially increased security.

(Pappas et al. 2021) openly aims for a robust solution with little necessary resources. It introduces IPLS, a fully decentralized federated learning framework that is partially based on the interplanetary file system (IPLS). Connecting to the private IPLS network allows any party

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to join or initiate an existing ML training process. Moreover, the solution is scalable, robust against attacks and sudden client departures or arrivals and reaches the accuracy of centralized federated learning. All important in order to achieve a practical IoT implementation, which is an explicit motivation of the authors. This project, similar to (Hu, Jiang, and Wang 2019), also considers model segmentation in order to minimize storage and bandwidth consumption, foregoing the possibility of issues with data distribution.

In summation, the research surrounding federated learning topology is very versatile and interesting for such a novel discipline. It presents a mix of very different approaches to the problem, some even exceedingly specific to a situation. However, there are few unifying works that would consider combining some of the solutions and attempt to reap the benefits stemming from both of them. Additionally, not all of these papers consider the specific conditions of edge computing and it therefore remains to be assessed, whether they would perform that well in that setting. Especially mechanisms such as acknowledging the physical distances between nodes in order to form the most energy-efficient connections remain to be integrated with other tools.

1.5.4. Federated learning tools

There is presently a versatile range of options when it comes to federated learning frameworks. Most of the below mentioned solutions are open source and therefore freely available for use and modification.

TensorFlow Federated Framework (*TensorFlow Federated: Machine Learning on Decentralized Data* accessed in 2022) focuses on employing Deep Learning solutions, developed in TensorFlow, on decentralized data. It therefore offers a wide variety of existing, stable models, but is limited by the capabilities of the core model library. Moreover, it currently only allows for simulation of the diverse runtime environments, which narrows down the testing possibilities. The sole availability of simulation mode affects also PySyft (OpenMined accessed in 2022), a project that is otherwise promising due to the high number of contributors involved.

FATE (*An Industrial Grade Federated Learning Framework* accessed in 2022), on the other hand, a framework that is currently open source and was donated to Linux Foundation by WeBank, allows for deployment both in simulation mode (standalone deployment) and federated mode (cluster deployment). It allows for manual installation, however, the use of Docker containers is recommended. Unfortunately, the deployment requirements of 6 GB of RAM as well as 100 GB of disk space on the device on server as well as on client cause it to be unsuitable for usage on far edge.

Similar limits pertain to PaddleFL (*PaddleFL* accessed in 2022), making it an option that

is otherwise well-developed, but sadly highly impractical in the context of this project. Finally, Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Framework (Daniel J.Beutel n.d.) allows for research on a diverse range of servers and devices, including mobile, Android, iOS, Raspberry Pi and Nvidia Jetson. It is additionally compatible with PyTorch, Keras and many more existing Machine Learning frameworks. It was build to endure real-world setups with up to 10.000 clients, which allows for robust experimentation, especially with the possibility of scaling the chosen topology.

Figure 1.3: Components of an edge computing-enabled smart city as imagined in (Khan et al. 2020a).

Figure 1.4: Homogenous and heterogenous data in a neighborhood grid (Bellet, Kermarrec, and Lavoie 2021).

Figure 1.5: This diagram depicts, in order, a star architecture as A, a ring architecture as B, a ring architecture with star-based groups as C and a star architecture with ring-based groups as D (Lee et al. 2020).

2. Methodology

2.1. Research design

2.1.1. Introduction

The main objective of this work concerns examining the stability and efficiency of various federated learning topology designs in conditions resembling those commonly found in IoT environments. To execute this goal, selected federated learning topologies were recreated in a containerized environment. Experiments were then conducted, using those topologies to train sample neural networks in conditions mimicking potential obstacles encountered on edge-based computing infrastructures, like connection issues between the server and the client or sudden client dropouts. Finally the results of the training, in the form of obtained neural networks and metrics gathered throughout the process, were thoroughly examined and used to estimate the effectiveness and robustness of a given topology.

To accomplish these goals, first a simple federated learning system with a centralized topology was implemented. Later, a few system designs were selected based on their ability to represent a specific trend in federated learning topology research and fulfill the architectural constraints of this study. Appropriate modifications were applied to the centralized solution in order to enable their implementation, including decentralized topological elements. Finally, experiments were carried out on the final system while simulating potential issues encountered in IoT space.

The conditions for all experiments were selected to be as similar as possible, with typically the same number of rounds and epochs of training, size of node groupings or severity of imposed constraints. The few exceptions apply to especially computationally expensive conditions, such as in the case of clustered federated learning, where the number of training rounds was considerably shortened. Additionally, the simulation of user dropout in some cases contained differences in the index of the training round, in which the user dropout occurred, as well as an increase in communication frequency for some topologies due to the limited memory of the employed environment. The technological basis for the implementation of the federated learning systems, as well the experimental conditions, consisted of a set of clients and servers, developed using

the Flower library (Beutel et al. 2020). These clients and servers were then encapsulated inside separate Docker containers in order to enable more sophisticated constraint simulation.

2.1.2. Topology choice

In order to properly showcase in this work a variety of approaches towards building a robust and scalable federated learning system, a curated example was selected for each prominent trend:

- **Centralized.** The structure consists of a server communicating with a group of clients as defined by (McMahan et al. 2016). This is the default implementation of a federated learning process offered by the Flower library without any necessary modifications.
- **Clustered.** The structure consists of a server communicating with a group of clients. Instead of sharing one model with all the clients, however, a clustered approach shares and aggregates the weights of multiple models simultaneously developed for different groups of clients. To represent this paradigm we have selected an iterative version as described in (Ghosh et al. 2020), in which the server simultaneously approximates the cluster identity of a given user and updates the appropriate cluster’s model based on the user data. This process repeats in every round of the training.
- **Hierarchical.** The structure consists of a server communicating with edge nodes, which then aggregate updates coming from clients (Mhaisen et al. 2022). Clients in hierarchical systems will also later be listed as far edge nodes, due to their implied distance from the central server, which is much more pronounced than that of an edge node. It is assumed in (ibid.) that the number of clients per edge node is more or less equal. Additionally, the server aggregates weights coming from the edge nodes according to Federated Averaging, whereas edge nodes, which are presumed to be located physically closer to far edge nodes and therefore have better network connection, aggregate weights in accordance to Federated SGD (Liu et al. 2020), which implies much more frequent communication.
- **Decentralized.** Due to the clear division of functionalities into constituting either a server or a client as defined in centralized topology in the tools available in the Flower library (Beutel et al. 2020), the development of a fully decentralized environment for experiments proved to be more difficult than those mentioned above. However, a solution combining elements of decentralized and centralized federated learning based on (Lee et al. 2020) was implemented. Guided by the conclusions from this study, which assessed star-based architecture with ring-based groups to have 26.7% higher accuracy than the state-of-the-art algorithms on a given task, this exact grouping principle (named there Tornadoes) was

2.2. SOLUTION ARCHITECTURE

selected. The combination of a star-based global schema with ring-based groups provided an opportunity to assess the robustness of ring-based groups to sudden user dropouts or connection problems, while also leveraging the implementation support of star-based schema in the Flower library and the ease of interpretation provided by results in the form of one centralized model.

These architecture choices were determined by the adherence of a given work to a selected paradigm, as well as the limitations imposed by the tools and environment chosen for this work.

2.2. Solution architecture

Some elements of the solution architecture were implemented upfront and later only adapted, with slight modifications, in order to simulate more sophisticated topologies. These common components and technologies served as a basis for all the later described systems.

2.2.1. Common elements

In order to implement the aforementioned topologies, there are two types of crucial elements: federated learning servers and clients. They will later be used in the constructed system as communicating components, remaining in constant contact with each other.

These components, in their implementation specific to this work, are later referred to as Training Collector and Local Operations. A Training Collector component possesses the capabilities of a federated learning centralized server, with the availability to start and manipulate model training with the use of specific aggregation algorithms and strategies. A Local Operations component, on the other hand, has the abilities of a federated learning client, with the main focus placed on local model training and dataset loading.

The training process for the centralized topology, which serves as a basis for result comparison in this study, proceeds as follows. First, an instance of Training Collector receives a training configuration. Secondly, the Training Collector begins waiting for a minimal number of clients as specified by the user. Then, a given number of Local Operations instances receive their training configuration similar in content to that supplied to the Training Collector, but also including identifying information about the Training Collector participating in process along a given instance of Local Operations. Later, the activated instances of Local Operations establish a gRPC connection with the Flower server on Training Collector. The server subsequently samples a given number of clients and provides them with model weights and, in some cases, additional configuration, which triggers the fit method on Local Operations. Local Operations instances fit

the model in parallel and return the weights along with any metrics they have gathered. After that, the weights are aggregated according to a strategy supplied by Training Collector. The data, along with any computed metrics, is similarly shared and gathered before and after model evaluation, which happens after each round. This approach, as it is here described in full, refers only to the training process in a centralized system, as it is a simple solution and a good basis for later implementations. It is then modified in order to construct following topologies.

The main components in this work, Local Operations and Training Collectors, are provided in the form of applications encapsulated in Docker containers. Each of the containers is equipped with a REST API server connected to an appropriate port on the training machine, used then for the user to initiate a federated learning process with a dynamically chosen set of parameters. The communication between containers is carried out according to the gRPC protocol by utilizing functionalities implemented as a part of the Flower library. Furthermore, all the containers forming the topology are connected to a common local Docker network called `custom_fl`.

2.2.2. Training Collector

In the system implementations presented in this study, Training Collector mainly serves the role of a server node. Uploading sample configuration data to the local endpoint `/job/config/{id}` starts the local Flower server, therefore initiating the training process in compliance with sent data. The data that can be provided to the server include type of aggregation algorithm used for federated learning, minimal number of clients necessary in order to start training, as well the minimum number of clients necessary for training each round, the fraction of clients to be sampled for training or evaluation, a set timeout for the responses coming from clients, the number of clients to choose for training with blacklisting and some additional values used for later testing.

The behaviour exhibited by the server before and after each training, as well as evaluation round is defined in the form of a Strategy class, in accordance with the Flower library. This class is used by the Flower server to group clients, selected from available client interfaces, with the appropriate weights to be later sent by the server, as well as define the mechanisms used to aggregate results from the clients and evaluate current model performance. Due to its periodic nature (methods are called in the defined order before and after each and every round), this class was also used for gathering metrics and saving current model weights for later analysis. The metrics, which were gathered after each training round, consisted of aggregated evaluation loss, as well as global evaluation loss and global accuracy. They were collected in order to provide efficient and accurate monitoring of the training process. Later, they were locally stored in the

2.2. SOLUTION ARCHITECTURE

container in the form of a serialized object inside a pickle file (Van Rossum 2020).

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Method:** POST
- URL:** /job/config/{id}/
- Parameters:** A table with columns 'Name' and 'Description'. The 'id' parameter is required and has the value '12'.
- Request body:** A JSON object with the following structure:

```
{
  "strategy": "avg",
  "model_id": "base",
  "num_rounds": "50",
  "min_fit_clients": "3",
  "min_available_clients": "3",
  "adapt_config": "custom",
  "timeout": "1080",
  "blacklisted": "1",
  "config": {
    "config_id": "min_effort",
    "batch_size": "64",
    "steps_per_epoch": "32",
    "epochs": "5",
    "learning_rate": "0.001"
  }
}
```
- Buttons:** 'Execute' (blue) and 'Clear' (white).

Figure 2.1: Sample training configuration provided to Training Collector

2.2.3. Local Operations

An instance of Local Operations, the analogue for a federated learning client used in this study, is created similarly to Training Collector. In order to start the training, it needs to be provided with a viable training configuration, most importantly including the address of a federated learning server it should be connected to.

A Local Operations component is responsible for loading and preprocessing the right subset of local data for a given client, as well as setting up the local model. It not only executes, but also enhances the behaviour of a federated learning client in the form of classes extending the `flower.client.Client` class, by implementing methods of initiating, fitting the model, and finally evaluating the client. This work leverages this innate periodicity of the client and uses it after each training round to save model weights and gather relevant metrics, most importantly evaluation accuracy and loss of the current model as computed on the local test set. The values of these metrics, in their original form as well as an average (in the case of aggregated loss - weighted average) over the metric values from all Local Operations, were then used to assess the efficiency of the training process. Similarly to Training Collector, these works are regularly stored in the form of serialized objects in a pickle file (ibid.).

2.3. Libraries and tools

In order to provide a basic implementation of a centralized federated learning topology, as well as later, more sophisticated architectural examples and simulate conditions needed to conduct later experiments, a wide range of different tools had to be employed.

2.3.1. Python

Systems recreating various topologies, as well as the programs preparing experiments were implemented in Python, which is a general-purpose, high-level programming language. It supports garbage collection and dynamic typing, as well as multiple programming paradigms from procedural to functional. It is consistently regarded as one of the most popular programming languages. Its design, above all, emphasises readability and simplicity (Van Rossum and Drake Jr 1995).

2.3.2. Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Framework

The features necessary for federated learning were developed in the study with the assistance of an existing framework, Flower. Its main advantages include extensive scalability, with workloads running up to 10.000 clients, compatibility with an extensive range of machine learning frameworks and platform independence. In addition, Flower offers fast default communication between enablers using the gRPC protocol (Beutel et al. 2020) (Daniel J.Beutel n.d.).

2.3.3. gRPC

By proxy of using the Flower framework, this work has employed gRPC to implement communication between Docker containers, in contrast to the configuration from the outside coming to the containers through RESTful endpoints. gRPC is an open source, high performance Remote Procedure Call (RPC) framework. It uses Protocol buffer (binary representation) to serialize payload data. The framework can be ran in any environment, as well efficiently connect edge devices to backend services while providing low-latency and high-throughput communication (Lee and Liu 2022).

2.3.4. Keras

Keras is an API written in Python and available as a part of the machine learning platform TensorFlow. Its main purpose involves enabling fast experimentation in the area of Deep Learning. This study employs Keras for the construction of the models used for execution of Federated

2.4. CENTRALIZED SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Learning experiments (Chollet et al. 2015).

2.3.5. FastAPI

To allow for the exchange of configuration files and additional information between enablers, HTTP endpoints will be implemented as well. The FastAPI framework was selected to do so. It was selected due to its very high performance, comparable with NodeJS and Go. It is also very intuitive, with extensive editor support provided, and compatible with standards such as OpenAPI and JSON Schema (Ramírez 2021).

2.3.6. Docker

In order to test the resulting federated learning topologies, multiple enablers will have to be ran and coordinated from one machine. Docker will be used to fulfill this task. Docker is a software framework that allows for building, running and managing containers on servers and the cloud. It allows for easy start, as well as graceful respawn and teardown of containers (Merkel 2014).

2.3.7. Pumba

Additional testing capabilities will be provided by Pumba (Ledenev 2021). Pumba is a testing tool designed for Docker containers. Its main functionalities involve the simulation of disturbances which may afflict the application in IoT environments, such as network failures or resource constraints. As such it is in accordance with the chaos engineering paradigm (Basiri et al. 2016).

2.4. Centralized system implementation

Since currently a centralized topology can be considered the default topology supported by Flower (Beutel et al. 2020), the solution did not need additional modifications in order to simulate a centralized system. Therefore the role of Local Operations and Training Collector in this case stayed as is, with the Training Collector periodically aggregating weights from all the Local Operations.

Figure 2.2: Topology of a sample centralized federated learning system

2.5. Clustered system implementation

A clustered architecture, as implemented according to (Ghosh et al. 2020), necessitates the training of multiple local models on each client in every local epoch and with that the need for increased computing capabilities on edge devices. Nevertheless, it also provides a more robust solution for clients with local data significantly differing from each other by developing a set number of final models. Additionally, the dynamic nature of the Iterative Federated Clustering Algorithm (IFCA) allows for quick recalculation of the clusters in the cases of incoming users or user dropout.

Figure 2.3: Topology of a clustered federated learning system

2.5.1. Logical differences

In order to implement a clustered system according to the description provided in (ibid.), a few modifications have to be applied. The function and placements of containers in the system remain unchanged, with Training Collector and Local Operations providing the functionalities of a server and a client respectively. The internal behaviours of the containers, however, has to be extensively modified.

Algorithm 1 Iterative Federated Clustering Algorithm (IFCA)

Require: number of clusters k , step size γ , $j \in [k]$, initialization $\theta_j^{(0)}$, number of parallel iterations T , number of local gradient steps τ (for model averaging)

for $t=0,1,\dots,T-1$ **do**

center machine: broadcast $\theta_j^{(t)}$, $j \in [k]$

$M_t \leftarrow$ random subset of working machines (participating devices)

for worker machine $i \in M_t$ **in parallel do**

cluster identity estimate $\hat{j} = \operatorname{argmin}_{j \in [k]} F_i(\theta_j^{(t)})$

define one-hot encoding vector $s_i = \{s_{i,j}\}_{j=1}^k$ with $s_{i,j} = \mathbf{1}\{j = \hat{j}\}$

option I (gradient averaging):

compute (stochastic) gradient: $g_i = \hat{\nabla} F_i(\theta_{\hat{j}}^{(t)})$, send s_i, g_i to center machine

option II (model averaging):

$\tilde{\theta}_i^{(0)} = \text{LocalUpdate}(\theta_{\hat{j}}^{(t)}, \gamma, \tau)$, send $s_i, \tilde{\theta}_i$ to center machine

end for

center machine:

option I(gradient averaging): $\theta_j^{(t+1)} = \theta_j^{(t)} - \frac{\gamma}{m} \sum_{i \in M_t} s_{i,j} g_i$, $\forall j \in [k]$

option II(model averaging): $\theta_j^{(t+1)} = \sum_{i \in M_t} s_{i,j} \tilde{\theta}_i / \sum_{i \in M_t} s_{i,j}$, $\forall j \in [k]$

end for

Ensure: $\theta_j^{(T)}$, $j \in [k] = 0$

LocalUpdate($\tilde{\theta}^{(0)}, \gamma, \tau$) at the i -th worker machine

for $q = 0, \dots, \tau - 1$ **do**

(stochastic) gradient descent $\tilde{\theta}^{(q+1)} = \tilde{\theta}^{(q)} - \gamma \hat{\nabla} F_i(\tilde{\theta}^{(q)})$

end for

Ensure: $\tilde{\theta}^{(\tau)} = 0$

Iterative Federated Clustering Algorithm aims to simultaneously conduct model training and dynamically estimate the cluster identity of a given client. To do so, in each iteration the server sends out k models to every client, where k is provided as a training parameter standing for the

number of clusters. In each training round instances of Local Operations simultaneously train k models and evaluate the cluster identity of the instance. The identity evaluation is conducted by computing the loss function of a cluster model on a part of the local dataset. The model that led to obtaining the lowest loss value is then sent out to the server along with the current cluster estimation of the instance, which is equal to the cluster identity of the model.

(Ghosh et al. 2020) also allows for early stopping of the estimation process at the point, in which the cluster identities of the instances cease to shift. This would result in the instances simply training the model of the cluster they belong to in a centralized fashion.

2.5.2. Modification implementation

In order to replicate IFCA with the constraints of our given study, a few modifications have to be applied. Some of those are necessitated by the lack of support from the Flower library regarding topologies more complex than a simple, centralized star architecture. For example, the current version of Flower Server and Client do not allow for the exchange of a few different models between Server and Client in each iteration.

To counteract it, this work uses Python multiprocessing library to run k Flower clients in parallel on one Local Operations component, each updating the model weights and computing the value of loss function for a given cluster model. To effectively communicate between clients this study employs the use of Python objects like multiprocessing.Queue, which allow various processes to share memory (albeit in a limited manner) and effectively communicate.

After each round every client puts the value of the cluster weights, the loss achieved by the model, its current cluster identity and the length of data used for training on the Queue. Every client also increments the value of priority. Priority in this case serves to indicate, how many other clients have already completed training of their cluster models. As a result, the last Flower client to finish achieves a priority value equal to the number of clusters−1. This client then empties the queue of stored data and, based on this, estimates the cluster identity in a given round. After finishing the estimation, the last client on Local Operations empties the queue, resets the priority value and sends the final results to the Training Collector.

As for the special behaviour of the Training Collector, its Strategy is modified in order to treat the Flower clients with the same IP address as representations of the same client and store its current cluster identity. Later, the Training Collector selects only the training results of the client with the highest priority for a given local IP address and stores its current cluster identity along with model weights. This stored data is later used after each round ends in order to aggregate

weights for a given cluster. In order to aggregate evaluation results from the local instances, on the other hand, the Training Collector sends out to the clients stored aggregated weights for the cluster currently estimated to include the local instance. Finally, evaluation results are also aggregated within the members of a given cluster.

The implementation developed for this study also allows for early stopping of the cluster identity estimation and later training of the Local Operations withing the last iteratively estimated cluster for each.

2.6. Hierarchical system implementation

A hierarchical topology implies a more sophisticated hierarchy than the one present in centralized systems, with additional levels of aggregation inserted between a global server and a client. Furthermore, the use of FedSGD between edge nodes and clients (in this work mentioned also as far edge nodes) suggest a communication round happening after every update of the local model weights, which is much more constant than for other topologies. This indicates the hierarchical topology to be a possible solutions for environments where there is a need to decrease the incoming communication for the global server, but it is possible to place additional nodes in close proximity to the client nodes.

Figure 2.4: Topology of a hierarchical federated learning system modelled on (Mhaisen et al. 2022)

2.6.1. Logical differences

Aside from a client and a server, hierarchical federated learning defines another type of node present in its topology - the edge node, which behaves like a client in relation to the server and like a server in relation to the clients (far edge nodes). It configures training of far edge nodes at the request of the server, aggregates the weights and later sends it to the server for further global aggregation. Additionally, the communication frequency between an edge node and far edge nodes is assumed to be significantly higher than between the global server and edge nodes (Mhaisen et al. 2022). The reasoning for this decision comes from the presumption that the server node, which is set to be located in the cloud, might have a more unstable connection with the far edge nodes than the local edge node. As a result, the aggregation protocol between server and the edge nodes can be defined as Federated Averaging and the protocol between edge nodes and far edge nodes as Federated SGD. In practice, this means that the aggregation round between edge nodes and far edge nodes should appear after every weight update applied on the far edge nodes. A common definition for FedSGD implies that the local far edge nodes should calculate this weight update based on all data present on the far edge node treated as a single batch (Liu et al. 2020). In order to decrease the amount of Random Access Memory needed to conduct experiments present in this work, however, in some cases the weight updates on far edge nodes were calculated based on just a part of the local dataset in each round. These concessions were employed for the experiments conducted only on the CIFAR-10 dataset, due to the preprocessing in this case involving the enlarging of the images and therefore increasing the amount of RAM memory needed to train the model. Additionally, the far edge nodes in this work are assumed to be divided more or less equally among edge nodes so as to adhere to a given in (Mhaisen et al. 2022) heuristic.

2.6.2. Modification implementation

In order to provide functionalities of hierarchical federated learning in the system presented in this work, the original implementations of Training Collector and Local Operations did not require many changes. The only meaningful difference was the addition of the possibility to train for only a step before aggregation on Local Operations, instead of for a whole epoch. To do so, an ImageDataGenerator as defined by the Keras library (Chollet et al. 2015) is used to produce an iterator, which can then remain stateful between rounds and be appropriately reset as soon as the model cycles through all the batches composing the training dataset.

Instead, a new type of node, which would combine the functionalities of Training Collector and Local Operations has to be defined. Edge component, implemented as a special case of

Figure 2.5: Example of a hierarchical learning process according to (Mhaisen et al. 2022)

the Local Operations component, leverages the functionalities of the Flower client in order to easily communicate with the global server. This is executed by combining the initiation of the `SpecialClientImplementation` instance with starting a gRPC connection using a Flower server. Then, in each iteration, instead of training the local model as a part of the original fit method the `SpecialClientImplementation` uses its own modified Flower server to request training from its clients. After a set number of rounds, the updated weights are aggregated in `SpecialClientImplementation` and sent back to the global server with additional information about the sum of the lengths of aggregated data.

2.7. Star-based system with ring-based groups implementation

A star architecture with ring-based groups allows for the investigation of decentralized elements while staying inside the implementation constraints necessitated by the limited development time and use of the Flower (Beutel et al. 2020) framework. More specifically, while additional means of communication between client nodes had to be supplemented, the global

Algorithm 2 Custom training behaviour of the edge component

Require: SpecialClientImplementation object *self*, parameters *p*, configuration *config*

```

0: function FIT(self, parameters, config)
1: print "Flower server running for config.num_rounds"
2: total_lengths  $\leftarrow$  0
3: self.model.weights  $\leftarrow$  parameters
4: params, lengths  $\leftarrow$  FIT_CLIENT_LOCAL(self.server, self.model.weights, self.round)
5: total_lengths  $\leftarrow$  total_lengths + lengths
6: for i = 0, 1, ..., self.num_local_rounds - 1 do
7:   params, lengths  $\leftarrow$  FIT_CLIENT_LOCAL(self.server, params, self.round)
8:   total_lengths  $\leftarrow$  total_lengths + lengths
9: end for
10: self.round  $\leftarrow$  self.round + 1
11: if self.round == ROUNDS then
    END_SERVER(self)
12: end if
13: return new_params, total_length

```

schema of the server aggregating data from clients was preserved. As a result, one final global model emerges from the training, which is easier to store and meaningfully compare with the products of training on other architectures than a large number of local models. The addition of ring-based groups, however, allows for the investigation of the effectiveness of decentralized elements.

2.7.1. Logical differences

The main logical difference between this topology and a basic centralized example described in this work involves additional communication between client nodes aside from the client-server connection. The process of training as described in (Lee et al. 2020) begins with setting up the node rings. Then for each round of the training for the set number of iterations every client belonging to the ring trains its local model and then propagates the updated weights to the next client in the chain. If a set number of local iterations is fulfilled, all of the models weights belonging to local nodes get aggregated by the global server.

Algorithm 3 Tornadoes (STAR-rings)

Require: $N, |G|, C, \tau_1, \tau_2$ **Ensure:** \mathbf{w}_T Initialize $\{w^{k,i}\}_{i \in N}$ to a random model \mathbf{w}_0 Initialize a random ring $[i_j \in N | j \in \mathbb{N}^0, i_{j+|N|} = i_j]$ $\{N^k\}_{k \in G} \leftarrow \text{CLUSTER}(N)$ **for** $t \leftarrow 0, \dots, T - 1$ **do** **for each** $k \in G$ **in parallel do** **for each** $c \leftarrow 0, \dots, C - 1$ **in parallel do** $j \leftarrow \lfloor t/\tau_1 \rfloor, i \leftarrow (i_j + c) \bmod |N^k|$ $\mathbf{w}_{t+1}^{k,i} \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_t^{k,i} - \eta \nabla F^{k,i}(\mathbf{w}_t^{k,i})$ **if** $t \bmod \tau_1$ **and** $t \bmod \tau_1 \tau_2 \neq 0$ **then** $i_{next} \leftarrow (i_{j+1} + c) \bmod |N^k|$ $\mathbf{w}_t^{k,i_{next}} \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_t^{k,i}$ **end if** **end for** **end for** **if** $t \bmod \tau_1 \tau_2 = 0$ **then** $\{\mathbf{w}_t^{k,i}\}_{k \in G, i \in N} \leftarrow \sum_{k \in G} \sum_{i \in N^k} \frac{|D^{k,i}|}{|D|} \mathbf{w}_t^{k,i}$ **end if****end for**

Figure 2.6: Topology of a federated learning system with local ring groups and centralized weight aggregation

2.7.2. Modification implementation

Since global weight aggregation as specified in (Lee et al. 2020) is still conducted according to a star-based schema, with one server node gathering clients from all the user nodes, there is no need to change the behaviour of Training Collector. However, the sudden involvement of communication that would transcend the standard relationship between a client and a server required significant improvements in the functioning of Local Operations. Due to the need to comply with objects and data formats defined by the Flower library, the training process was written in a way that would repurpose as much of the existing communication functionalities as possible.

In the final implementation of this system each Local Operations instance includes essentially two types of clients and a server: BigClient, SmallClient and DecentralizedServer. The training process begins with BigClient connecting to the central Training Collector component and activating local training. Then, for each round, BigClient propagates the current model weights belonging to its model to the next node in the chain, using the Decentralized Server object to establish connection with the Small Client belonging to the next node in the chain. Subsequently,

it waits for its own SmallClient to receive weights from the previous node in the chain, perform training and use the weights later to update local model weights for BigClient.

Algorithm 4 Custom training behaviour of the BigClient

Require: BigClient object *self*, parameters *p*, configuration *config*

```

0: function FIT(self, parameters, config)
1: self.model.weights  $\leftarrow$  parameters
2: lengths  $\leftarrow$  0
3: for  $n = 0, 1, \dots, self.rounds$  do
4:   print "Fit in round  $n$ "
5:    $l \leftarrow$  FIT_CLIENT_LOCAL(self.server, self.model.weights,  $n$ , lengths)
6:   current_event_set  $\leftarrow$  IS_SET(self.client.events[ $n$ ])
7:   print "Waiting for current_event_set"
8:   WAIT(self.client.events[ $n$ ])
9:   lengths  $\leftarrow$  self.client.lengths
10:  self.model.weights  $\leftarrow$  self.client.model.weights
11:  current_event_set  $\leftarrow$  IS_SET(self.client.events[ $n$ ])
12:  print "Cleared flag for current_event_set"
13: end for
14: for  $e \in self.clients.events$  do
15:   CLEAR( $e$ )
16: end for
17: self.client.current_round  $\leftarrow$  0
18: return self.model.weights, self.client.lengths

```

However, since training on both types of clients is triggered by processes running outside of a given container (Training Collector and the previous Local Operations instance in the chain), additional mechanisms were added in the form of multithreading for the sake of synchronization. Most importantly, both the SmallClient as well as the BigClient have access to a given set of multithreading Events. These are then unlocked with every local epoch, allowing the thread which includes BigClient to start the propagation as soon as SmallClient ends its iteration training and sets the value of a given Event. After the execution of a given number of local rounds conducted on a single node, the Event set gets reset.

2.8. Training evaluation

During the execution of the experiments multiple metrics were gathered. Their main purpose was enabling further analysis and comparison of the results. Their characteristics and reasoning for their inclusion are as presented.

2.8.1. Metrics measured every round

Some of the metrics presented in this work were gathered after every round of federated training in order to visualize the speed and smoothness of convergence for training on specific topologies.

- **Aggregated evaluation loss.** This metric can be understood as the mean of evaluation loss function values on each of the clients, with the evaluation being conducted on the local test data with distribution identical to local training data. Aggregated evaluation loss showcases the speed of training of the model on local data. In the case of experiments conducted on the clustered architecture, due to the unstable adherence of a given client to a cluster more precision was needed. For this reason, a weighted mean instead of a mean of evaluation loss was measured. The weights of the mean are influenced by the number of examples present in each of the local test sets. In the figures involving both clustered and centralized architecture, weighted mean of evaluation loss was displayed for both of them. A similar metric was also employed in (Rehman et al. 2021).
- **Aggregated accuracy.** Similarly to the aggregated evaluation loss, this metric is the mean of accuracy values for all client nodes as measured on the local test set after each round. It indicates, how accurate are the model predictions on local test set after any given round of training. Aggregated, or average accuracy for the models trained on the local data on each client was also measured in (Ek et al. 2021b).
- **Global accuracy.** This metric is used in the case of experiments involving clustered architecture as a comparison to aggregated evaluation loss. Since the implicit focus of IFCA is developing models that would perform the best on the data of the clients belonging to a set cluster, the speed and smoothness of convergence for this subset local data as well as global data may differ greatly. Global accuracy serves as an indication of performance on the whole test set.

2.8.2. Metrics measured on the final model

Some of the metrics were also used to measure the performance of the final model, which was treated as the end product of the training. These measurements were, in all cases, conducted on the entirety of the test set for a given dataset. Measures such as precision, recall and F1 score were separately gathered for each of the categories present in the dataset, with the values for all categories computed as unweighted mean per label. Additionally, total accuracy was also calculated.

- Precision. Computes the proportion of number of values predicted to belong to a given category, to the number of values predicted to belong to a given category which actually belong to a given category (Powers 2008).
- Recall. Computes the proportion of number of values which actually belong to a given category to the number of all values predicted to belong to a given category (ibid.).
- F1 score. Defined as the harmonic mean of recall and precision (Sasaki 2007).

2.9. Constraint simulation

An important component of the experiments is measuring the metrics, as defined above, for the training processes with and without given constraints imposed on them. This is done in order to test the resilience and suitability of chosen architectures in selected IoT environments.

2.9.1. Sudden user dropout

In order to simulate sudden user dropout after a specified round, the appropriate client node was removed using Pumba.

Listing 2.1: Pumba commands used for simulating user dropout

```
./pumba_linux_amd64 kill appv9-local_operations-1
```

Additionally, system behaviours that would keep the system active and therefore allow for evaluation of later results were assumed. For example, the previous node in a ring-based group immediately connects to the next node in the chain in the case of a severed connection. Moreover, the server is set in these cases to accept the `min_fit_clients` as an acceptable number of nodes for later training, even if it's lesser than `min_available_clients`.

Listing 2.2: Node behaviour in a ring-based group in the case of severed connection in chain

```

to_connect_index = int(os.environ.get("TO_CONNECT"))
group_size = int(os.environ.get("GROUP_SIZE"))
to_connect = f"appv{to_connect_index}_local_operations_1:8080"
try:
    start_numpy_client(to_connect, client)
except Exception as err:
    log(INFO, f"Caught_exception_{err}")
    new_index = (to_connect_index + 1) % group_size +
                ((to_connect_index+1)//group_size)*group_size
    to_connect = f"appv{new_index}_local_operations_1:8080"
    start_numpy_client(to_connect, client)

```

2.9.2. Network connection with interruptions

In order to simulate an unstable internet connection between a server and a client, a mechanism of blacklisting was developed. This was executed by adding an appropriate condition to Strategy class, which will first pick a stated number of random clients to add to the blacklist. Then, every second round the clients from the blacklist are updated with their own, unchanged weights (in order to both fulfill constraints introduced by the Flower library and update each client with new weights each round, while preserving the effect of the blacklisted client not receiving new information). Additionally, after the end of every second round the updates from the blacklisted clients are not taken into account during weight aggregation.

2.9.3. Geographical constraints

This study will explore cases of unequal user node groupings due to the assumption that the number of nodes will not be equally divided between geographical areas and therefore there may be a higher number of clients available for grouping in some areas rather than the other. Additionally, the number of client nodes may dynamically change in areas with a set number of edge nodes, which may then lead to unequal groupings of clients. Therefore tests with unequal groupings of clients will be conducted.

Geographical constraints were, if possible, imposed on the examples of different topologies with similar schemes for user grouping in order to easily compare the final results. For example, training on both hierarchical architectures, as well as star architectures with ring-based groups was conducted for clients divided into 2 groups of 4 clients and 3 groups of 2 clients, 2 clients and 1 client. In the case of centralized architecture, no constraints were imposed due to the

2.10. SYSTEM LIMITATION

topology not employing any forms of grouping. For clustered architectures, on the other hand, the number of clients belonging to a given cluster was dynamically computed as a part of the training process. In these cases, simply a constraint in the form of different number of clusters participants in the training was tested.

2.9.4. Data distribution

The use of federated learning in Internet of Things environments means, that the local data used for training will often have a data distribution significantly differing from the global data distribution. In many cases, due to the privacy constraints the server will not be able to access information about this difference directly, which may impair its ability to properly group the clients in order to compensate. Without focusing entirely on this topic, the experiments were conducted both using data divided into local sets, in which the distribution was identical to the global distribution, as well as in which the data distribution on each client was unique and different from the global distribution. This choice was made in order to showcase the influence of local distribution on the final results in edge cases, in which grouping the nodes in any way would not restore its adherence to the global distribution.

2.10. System limitation

Experiments were conducted using Docker on a virtual machine equipped with up to 60 GB RAM and 14 virtual cores. However, due to the high computing needs of Deep Learning as well as conducting computations multiple Docker containers, this setup effectively allows for simulations of a system consisting of up to 8 clients at a time. Due to the focus of this work involving simulating the forms of communication and device encapsulation present in IoT, this scalability concession was ultimately deemed to be worth it.

2.11. Datasets and models

2.11.1. CIFAR-10

The CIFAR-10 dataset includes 60000 coloured images 32 pixels wide and 32 pixels high, belonging to 10 classes, which is a small subset of the original 80 million Tiny Images dataset (Krizhevsky 2009). This dataset was chosen both because of its considerable size, as well as its balanced nature and ease of visualization. Its common appearance in literature should addition-

Listing 1: Docker Compose file used to generate the Local Operations container for experiments on the CIFAR-10 dataset

ally increase the reproducibility of this research.

The dataset is, by default, divided into a set of 50000 training images and 10000 test images. All classes encountered in the dataset are completely mutually exclusive, with 6000 examples of each of them. Therefore the CIFAR-10 dataset may be considered balanced. Pixel values of the images in the dataset have been normalized and rescaled to be 128 pixels high and 128 pixels wide to before training as a part of the preprocessing process. They were not additionally augmented in any way. The images have been divided equally and with preservation of the original label distribution for all clients participating in the experiments.

For the tests carried out on this dataset a Convolutional Neural Network was used. The model consisted of 18 layers, including 6 convolutional layers and three dense layers with 2915114 parameters in total. The local training is carried out using Stochastic Gradient Descent with beginning learning rate of 0.01, momentum of 0.9 and learning rate decay of 0.5. The model is employing categorical crossentropy as its loss function.

In preparation for the experiments, data belonging to the CIFAR-10 dataset was divided equally between eight client nodes with preservation of the global distribution on the local scale. The division concerned the training data as well as the testing data, which means that the aggregated accuracy on the local clients is more or less equal to the global model accuracy.

2.11.2. German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark

The German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (Stallkamp et al. 2012) is a multi-class, single-image classification challenge which was held at the International Joint Conference on Neural Networks in 2011. This dataset was chosen as a basis for experiments in this work due to the arguably large size of categories of its labels, which later allowed for easy manipulation of local data distribution. Additionally, the small size of the images allowed for the experiments to be conducted faster.

The benchmark dataset used in this challenge consists of more than 50000 images belonging to 43 classes, with 39209 of them allocated for training and 12630 left as a test set. Due to its resemblance to real-life datasets, as well as its relatively small size, it was chosen to be further used as a basis for topological experiments. As part of the preprocessing, all images were scaled to the height and width of 32 pixels. In order to mimic varying distributions, the data on each client was generated to contain roughly the same number of examples of training data, with examples

on each user belonging to an entirely different set chosen from 43 categories. This indicates that the data distribution on each client varies from the global distribution and from the distribution on all of the other clients. Out of the data available on the user, 90% was used for training with 10% left for the evaluation of aggregated accuracy. The aggregated local accuracy as a metric in this dataset serves as a comparison to the global accuracy, with the local test sets mirroring the distribution of local data, whereas the global test set adheres to the global distribution and therefore serves as a source of information on the global performance of a model.

The model used during training was a Convolutional Neural Network, consisting of 5 convolutional layers and 3 dense layers. The local training was carried out using Adam as training optimizer and categorical crossentropy as the loss function.

Listing 2.3: The distribution of categories per a specific user

```
division = {0: [0, 1, 2], 1: [3, 4], 2: [5, 6, 7, 8, 9],
            3: [10, 11], 4: [12, 13, 14, 15, 16],
            5: [17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24],
            6: [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34],
            7: [35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42]}
```


(a) Category 7

(b) Category 20

(c) Category 30

(d) Category 38

Figure 2.7: Images from German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

3. Results

In order to avoid redundancy only the most meaningful results were displayed in this work. The rest can be found in the public repository mentioned later as Appendix 1.

3.1. Centralized architecture

3.1.1. Experiments on the CIFAR-10 Dataset

The experiments conducted on the centralized topology not only served as a way to analyze the robustness of this specific solution, but also as an important basis for comparison with other approaches presented in this work. The first experiments, results of which are exhibited in this work, were configured to run on the CIFAR-10 dataset with 8 local clients, training for 16 rounds with 5 local epochs carried out between each aggregation. The data distribution on the client nodes is more or less equal to the global data distribution.

Figure 3.3 shows the aggregated accuracy, as well as the aggregated evaluation loss for training with no interruptions and training with one user being blacklisted. The line shown on the figures is an average for a given metric in each round for all training nodes, with the vertical lines indicating the range of values found on the local nodes. In this case, these lines are relatively short, which means that the local values of metrics are relatively close to each other.

Surprisingly, the performance of the training with impaired communication seems to achieve better results, with accuracy slightly higher than for the uninterrupted case throughout the training. This statement is also supported by the metrics in Table 3.1.

A potential explanation may involve the fact that the local data distribution is so similar to the global data distribution. This may cause the model performance to relatively decrease as a result of weights aggregation when in comparison with further local training.

Similarly, the performance of the final model, as well as during the training seems to slightly increase with earlier user dropout. The final results achieved by the model with earlier and later dropout seem to be both equivalent and higher than uninterrupted training, as shown in Table 3.1, while the metrics gathered throughout training depicted in Figure 3.4 indicate better results

for earlier dropout. These results also suggest diminishing returns for weight aggregation in the case of identical global and local distribution on the client.

Table 3.1: Summary of experiment results of centralized architecture on CIFAR-10 dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.71	0.72	0.71	0.72
Blacklisting	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73
User dropout in round 4	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73
User dropout in round 14	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73

3.1.2. Experiments on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

Later experiments for the centralized topology employed the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset. The models were trained by 8 local clients for 40 rounds with 1 local epochs carried out between each aggregation. The data distribution on the client nodes differed from the the global data distribution, as well as the data distribution on every other node. The number of examples on every node was, however, more or less similar.

As presented on Figure 3.6, the differences in accuracy and evaluation loss between single nodes seem to be much more significant than in the case of the CIFAR-10 dataset, with a much less smooth training curve, possibly as a result of the differing local distributions (which includes the differing distribution of the local test data). However, they seem to be decreasing in later rounds. The learning curve in this case seems to be much more similar for the training with blacklisting and in uninterrupted training than in the case of the CIFAR-10 dataset. Table 3.2, however, shows markedly better final results for the uninterrupted training.

Analogously, the training with user dropout in 30th round, shown on Figure 3.6, seems to underperform when compared to both dropout in round 10th as well as training without any interruptions. However, since the aggregated metrics in this case measure the process of learning on the local data and therefore do not account for any data lost along with the dropped out user, a comparison with the global accuracy of the resulting model is needed. The data in Table 3.2 supports the thesis of later user dropout forming the worst performing conditions of all for centralized architecture in this case. However, whereas the aggregated accuracy for the training with user dropout in 10th round seems to be significantly higher than for the training with no interruptions, the results shown in Table 3.2 paint a very different picture. This divergence, possibly suggesting the damage in aggregated metrics for the remaining models during training to be somewhat transient, with aggregated accuracy ultimately benefiting from a narrower focus

3.2. HIERARCHICAL ARCHITECTURE

stemming from a smaller number of differing distributions throughout training, is nevertheless worth noticing.

Table 3.2: Summary of experiment results of centralized architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.93
Blacklisting	0.91	0.89	0.89	0.91
User dropout in round 10	0.83	0.84	0.82	0.86
User dropout in round 30	0.83	0.81	0.80	0.81

3.2. Hierarchical architecture

3.2.1. Experiments on the CIFAR-10 Dataset

The experiments on hierarchical architecture were conducted both in cases with 2, as well as 3 edge nodes present, with 8 client nodes divided more or less equally between the edge nodes. The training conducted on the CIFAR-10 dataset took place for 16 rounds, with 5 local epochs conducted before aggregation in each round in the form of Federated SGD between the edge nodes and its client nodes. In order to minimize the amount of memory needed to conduct this experiment, the client nodes did not treat the whole local dataset as one batch during local training, instead updating the local model based on its fraction and immediately communicating the results to the appropriate edge node. The local data distribution on the client nodes was very similar to the global data distribution.

The results of hierarchical training with 2 edge nodes shown on Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8 indicate better performance for uninterrupted training than with training with any imposed constraint, with the round of user dropout not seeming to particularly influence the results. These statements are in a large part confirmed by the results shown in table 3.3, with the performance with later user dropout being slightly better than with interrupted communication and earlier user dropout as well. The more significant result of impaired communication, in comparison with centralized architecture, may stem from the fact, that the blacklisting between an edge node and a server node influence not only the course of training on a single client node, but the whole group of 4 client nodes.

The data gathered during hierarchical training on the CIFAR-10 dataset for 3 edge nodes, as

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79
Blacklisting	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
User dropout in round 1	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
User dropout in round 7	0.78	0.78	0.77	0.78

Table 3.3: Summary of experiment results of hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on CIFAR-10 dataset

Table 3.4: Summary of experiment results of hierarchical architecture with 3 edge nodes on CIFAR-10 dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78
Blacklisting	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76
User dropout in round 4	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
User dropout in round 12	0.76	0.75	0.75	0.75

depicted on Table 3.4 is comparable with the results gathered during hierarchical training for 2 edge nodes.

Although the relative influence of various constraints on communication for hierarchical topology can yield important conclusions, it is also crucial to consider the quality of final results as compared to other architectures. Figure 3.9 hints, that for a comparable number of local epochs of training a hierarchical topology achieves significantly better results than the centralized one, especially in the case of 2 nodes. Metrics gathered on the test set in Tables 3.1, 3.3 and 3.4 appear to confirm this statement.

3.2.2. Experiments on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

The experiments were conducted on the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset for 8 rounds of global aggregation carried out between the server and edge nodes, each interspersed with 5 rounds of local aggregation between the edge node and its assigned clients. In this case, since the training carried out on the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset was comparatively less memory intensive, in order to be more faithful to the original paradigm of Federated SGD the client nodes updated their weights in each iteration based on the whole local dataset treated as one batch. Additionally, the data on each client node had a different distribution than the data on all the other client nodes, as well as the global data.

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In the case of hierarchical topology with 2 edge nodes, the differences between the measurements gathered throughout training for different client nodes depicted on the Figure 3.10 and 3.11 appear distinctly more pronounced than those in experiments conducted on the CIFAR-10 dataset. Additionally, whereas the training with interrupted communication for one user achieved better performance than the training with no interruptions, as supported by global accuracy in Table 3.5, training with earlier user dropout caused little to no difference in measurements gathered on the final model, with only late user dropout leading to noticeable deterioration. It is interesting to note that the more frequent aggregation of model weights locally trained on very much different distributions might have an averse effect. Comparable results were achieved for experiments conducted on hierarchical topology with 3 edge nodes.

Table 3.5: Summary of experiment results of hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.19
Blacklisting	0.11	0.14	0.09	0.23
User dropout in round 3	0.06	0.09	0.05	0.19
User dropout in round 6	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.14

Table 3.6: Summary of experiment results of hierarchical architecture with 3 edge nodes on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.03	0.06	0.02	0.11
Blacklisting	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.09
User dropout in round 3	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.17
User dropout in round 6	0.18	0.21	0.16	0.34

Table 3.6 indicates, that the training of hierarchical topology with three edge nodes on the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset faces similar issues to an analogous training with 2 edge nodes.

As emphasised again on Figure 3.12, for a comparable number of local epochs the performance of centralized architecture is vastly better than for hierarchical architectures. Possible ways to mitigate this issue may involve more frequent global aggregation and grouping the nodes to recreate the global data distribution in group, although both of these techniques may not always

be suitable for implementation in edge environments.

3.3. Star architecture with ring-based groups

3.3.1. Experiments on the CIFAR-10 Dataset

The experiments for star architecture with ring-based groups were conducted for 2 topological distributions: first with 2 rings, each constructed from 4 client nodes and second with 3 rings, 2 of them constructed from 3 client nodes and 1 from 2 client nodes. In both cases the training was conducted for 16 rounds with 5 local epochs between each round conducted locally, in this case by sending the local model to the next node in the chain after each epoch and then fitting the model incoming from the previous node on the local data. There were 8 client nodes participating in the training process, with data distribution on each similar to the global distribution.

The very small disparities between aggregated evaluation loss and accuracy for all client nodes in each round seen in Figures 3.13 and 3.14, as well as the robustness towards both user dropout and interrupted communication, which seem to have little to no influence on the convergence, may be connected to additional weight updates inside the rings. The local model propagation provides an additional, more frequent mode of communication, which could add extra resilience to the training process. The global metrics visible on Table 3.7 point to a similar quality of the resulting model, with slight advantage given to training with communication interruptions.

Table 3.7: Experiment results of star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on CIFAR-10 dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78
Blacklisting	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79
User dropout in round 6	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78
User dropout in round 12	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78

Similarly, the results of the training conducted on an architecture with 3 groups with a smaller number of nodes seem to be very resilient to any communication failures. The resulting model, however, seems to exhibit slightly lower performance (shown on Table 3.8) than for products of federated learning on 2 ring-based groups (Table 3.7).

Finally, compared to the results obtained on experiments conducted on centralized architecture, the star based architecture consistently outperforms the base results (Figure 3.15), exhibiting performance very similar to hierarchical architecture on this exact dataset while needing less

3.3. STAR ARCHITECTURE WITH RING-BASED GROUPS

Table 3.8: Experiment results of star architecture with 3 ring-based groups on CIFAR-10 dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
Blacklisting	0.78	0.78	0.77	0.78
User dropout in round 1	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77
User dropout in round 8	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.77

total client nodes and additional communication.

3.3.2. Experiments on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

Tests done on the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset followed the formula of 8 with each ending with global weight aggregation, and in between 5 epochs of training carried out inside of a ring-based group. However, in this case the local data contained only a few of all categories forming the whole dataset, with no existing overlap in data with other client nodes. The grouping algorithm described in (Lee et al. 2020) was not used on this occasion due to both the extreme case of this local data distribution, which could considerably hinder the improvement of the grouping algorithm, as well as the focus on this work being placed more on general topology than grouping principles.

Metrics gathered throughout training of the star architecture with ring-based groups, as represented on Figures 3.16 and 3.17, regardless of the momentary conditions show little to no progress being made in the process of training. The resulting model achieves accuracy close to the accuracy of a random draw on this dataset (Table 3.9).

Table 3.9: Summary of experiment results of star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.04
Blacklisting	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06
User dropout in round 3	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.04
User dropout in round 6	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06

Training on an architecture with 3 ring-based groups yield very similar results to the experiments conducted on the architecture with 2 ring-based groups, both in the case of lack of visible convergence as well as low capabilities of the final model (Table 3.11).

Table 3.10: Summary of experiment results of star architecture with 3 ring-based groups on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy
No interruptions	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.04
Blacklisting	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06
User dropout in round 3	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.05
User dropout in round 6	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.06

Table 3.11: Summary of experiment results of star architecture with 3 ring-based groups on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Comparing the performance of the centralized architecture and star architecture with ring-based groups (Figure 3.18) reveals the much greater performance of the centralized architecture for the same number of training epoch, which may be tied to the robustness of a given architecture to variability in local data distribution.

3.4. Clustered architecture

3.4.1. Experiments on the CIFAR-10 Dataset

The experiments on clustered architecture were carried out both for 4 possible clusters, as well as 2. However, due to how resource-intensive these experiments are because of the necessity of training 2 to 4 times as many models per round, in some cases these experiments were shortened to take place for a lower number of rounds or experienced sudden interruptions. For this reason the number of rounds that have ultimately finished execution for selected tests varied. The original schema of 5 local epochs conducted between each round did not change, though.

In the case of the local data distribution similar to the global data distribution for the training with 2 clusters, one of the clusters frequently stops being updated early on (Figures 3.19, 3.20, 3.22) and the second subsequently behaves like a centralized learning system. In the case of Figure 3.20 both clusters kept being updated, albeit with one cluster being selected by some of the clients only in a couple rounds. The resulting models, however, underperformed compared to the centralized system both in the case of accuracy on the global test set, as well as the aggregated loss which refers only to the test sets of the clients choosing to train a given model. Similar issues plagued the experiments conducted on 4 clusters, in which only one cluster model was updated by all of the client nodes.

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

Table 3.12: Evaluation accuracy for each of the 2 clusters of clustered architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Cluster 0	Cluster 1
No interruptions	0.10	0.81
Blacklisting	0.36	0.47
User dropout in round 7	0.26	0.60
User dropout in round 14	0.33	0.52

3.4.2. Experiments on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

Tests conducted on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset could be divided into two types: the tests concerning a clustered architecture with 4 clustered models training in parallel, which were conducted for 20 epochs (in order to minimize their memory consumption) as well as tests concerning a clustered architecture with 2 clustered models, which were trained for 40 rounds. Both versions update the cluster models based on the one epoch of local training before each round of global aggregation. In the case of German Traffic Sign Benchmark Dataset and its division into 8 local subsets, which was previously defined in this work, it is important to note how different the data distribution on the local client (which also means test data distribution) is between the local clients and how a model that might be very effective for the subset of clients which belong to its cluster may not perform so well on the global test set.

As shown on Figures 3.23, 3.24, 3.25 and 3.26 in the case of German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset the cluster models are rarely abandoned during the training. Instead, both of the models typically reach low values of aggregated evaluation loss, which points to good performance on the data distribution on the clients belonging to a given cluster. The global accuracy for both models typically converges to a set point lower than the models trained on centralized architecture. An interesting feature to notice is the uneven nature of the learning curve, with occasional large spikes in aggregated loss, which translate to smaller drops in values of global accuracy, as depicted on Figure 3.24. This might point to the potential instability of the clustered architecture, especially implemented using Iterative Federated Clustering Algorithm, which dynamically assigns client nodes to the appropriate cluster. The sudden shifts in assignment might translate to value increases in aggregated evaluation loss, which should be significantly higher on data from a distribution new to the model. This suggestion may be supported by the echoed changes in performance of the other participating cluster.

Since the data on each client node contains a mutually exclusive, differing subset of categories,

Table 3.13: F1 score for each of the 2 clusters of clustered architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Category	Cluster 0	Cluster 1
0	0.00	0.93
1	0.00	0.94
2	0.00	0.86
3	0.00	0.89
4	0.00	0.91
5	0.00	0.80
6	0.00	0.80
7	0.00	0.95
8	0.00	0.87
9	0.00	0.83
10	0.00	0.86
11	0.00	0.87
12	0.00	0.95
13	0.00	0.98
14	0.00	0.63
15	0.00	0.97
16	0.00	0.83
17	0.55	0.00
18	0.32	0.00
19	0.81	0.00
20	0.19	0.00
21	0.03	0.00
22	0.36	0.00
23	0.17	0.00
24	0.13	0.00
25	0.00	0.94
26	0.00	0.47
27	0.00	0.57
28	0.00	0.77
29	0.00	0.70
30	0.00	0.53
31	0.00	0.77
32	0.00	0.59
33	0.00	0.94
34	0.00	0.89
35	0.00	0.96
36	0.00	0.95
37	0.00	0.92
38	0.00	0.92
39	0.00	0.92
40	0.00	0.68
41	0.00	0.62
42	0.00	0.00

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

and both of the models train on a portion of the local nodes, it is noteworthy to look into the scores achieved by each cluster model for a given subcategory. Table 3.13 depicts the F measure for both of the clusters. Curiously, in the cases in which one model achieves non-zero values for a given category, the other does not follow suit. This seems to indicate that values of global accuracy presented on 3.12 may not be fully representative when referring to the local test sets of these client nodes.

To compare the performance of the clustered training on the local data subsets belonging to specific clusters to the performance of centralized federated learning on the whole local test set, the aggregated evaluation loss of both measured in specific training circumstances was plotted. For uninterrupted training, Figure 3.27a shows the aggregated evaluation loss for one cluster to be consistently lower than for the centralized model, with the other reaching a similar value. Figure 3.27b demonstrates the effect of interrupted communication on clustered architecture, with the aggregated loss of one cluster model visibly oscillating around a value higher than the final aggregated loss value of both the centralized, as well as the other cluster model. Interrupted communication seems, in this case, destructive to the stability of the training.

The final values of aggregated evaluation loss for both cluster models training with dropout after the 10th round (Figure 3.28a) are either lower or equal than for centralized training. However, there are significant instabilities in the training process visible for the model of cluster 0. For training with user dropout after the 30th round (Figure 3.28b) the situation shifts a little, with both of the cluster models consistently receiving better results than the centralized model. However, albeit subdued, the instability in values of aggregated evaluation loss remains.

Surprising results can be observed in the case of a clustered architecture with 4 clusters, which involve mainly increased instability (Figures 3.29, 3.30, 3.31 and 3.32). Although the effect of some of the model clusters ceasing to update still happens in some cases, in most all of the model train concurrently, potentially swapping client nodes and leading to a lackluster performance both globally, looking at the global accuracy, as well as on the local datasets of client nodes belonging to the cluster, looking at the aggregated evaluation loss. This suggests, that a too large of a cluster number may yield detrimental effects throughout the training process.

The performance on specific categories, as depicted on Table 3.15, is frequently poor for all of the cluster models. On the other hand, some of the categories (10 and 11) yield positive F-measure scores for multiple cluster models, which also suggests unreliability in their cluster identities, with clients shifting between multiple clusters.

Table 3.14: Evaluation accuracy for each of the 4 clusters of clustered architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Experiment category	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
No interruptions	0.09	0.25	0.10	0.13
Blacklisting	0.28	0.15	0.16	0.10
User dropout in round 7	0.24	0.16	0.15	0.13
User dropout in round 14	0.26	0.08	0.15	0.17

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

Figure 3.1: Aggregated evaluation loss

Figure 3.2: Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.3: Comparison of training results for centralized architecture on training with no interruptions and with interrupted averaging on CIFAR-10

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.4: Comparison of training results for centralized architecture on training with no interruptions, with user dropout after 4th round and user dropout after 14th round on CIFAR-10

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.5: Comparison of training results for centralized architecture on training with no interruptions and with interrupted communication for one node on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.6: Comparison of training results for centralized architecture on training with no interruptions, with user dropout after 10 round and user dropout after 30th round for one node on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.7: Comparison of training results for hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on training with no interruptions and with interrupted averaging on CIFAR-10

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.8: Comparison of training results for hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on training with no interruptions, with user dropout after 1st round and user dropout after 7th round on CIFAR-10

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.9: Comparison of training results for hierarchical and centralized architecture on CIFAR-

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.10: Comparison of training results for hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on training with no interruptions and with interrupted communication for one node on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.11: Comparison of training results for hierarchical architecture with 2 edge nodes on training with no interruptions, training with user dropout after 3rd round and user dropout after 6th round on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.12: Comparison of training results for centralized and hierarchical architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.13: Comparison of training results for star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on training with no interruptions and training with interrupted communication for one node on CIFAR-10 dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.14: Comparison of training results for star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on training with no interruptions, training with user dropout after 6th round and user dropout after 12th round on CIFAR-10 dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.15: Comparison of training results for star architecture with ring-based groups and centralized architecture on CIFAR-10

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.16: Comparison of training results for star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on training with no interruptions and with interrupted communication for one node on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.17: Comparison of training results for star architecture with 2 ring-based groups on training with no interruptions, training with user dropout after 3rd round and user dropout after 6th round on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark Dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Aggregated accuracy

Figure 3.18: Comparison of training results for star architecture with ring-based groups and centralized architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.19: Results of training with no interruptions for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on CIFAR-10 dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.20: Results of training with interrupted communication for one node for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on CIFAR-10 dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.21: Results of training with user dropout after 3rd round for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on CIFAR-10 dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.22: Results of training with user dropout after 11th round for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on CIFAR-10 dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.23: Results of training with no interruptions for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.24: Results of training with interrupted communication for one node for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.25: Results of training with user dropout after 10th round for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.26: Results of training with user dropout after 30th round for clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Uninterrupted training

(b) Training with interrupted communication for one user

Figure 3.27: Comparison of experiments on centralized and clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

(a) Training with user dropout after 10th round

(b) Training with user dropout after 30th round

Figure 3.28: Comparison of experiments on centralized and clustered architecture with 2 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.29: Results of training with no interruptions for clustered architecture with 4 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.30: Results of training with interrupted communication for one node for clustered architecture with 4 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.31: Results of training with user dropout after 7th round for clustered architecture with 4 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

(a) Aggregated evaluation loss

(b) Global accuracy

Figure 3.32: Results of training with user dropout after 14th round for clustered architecture with 4 clusters on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

3.4. CLUSTERED ARCHITECTURE

Table 3.15: F1 score for each of the 4 clusters of clustered architecture on German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark dataset

Category	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	0.12	0.44	0.00	0.00
11	0.29	0.39	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	0.48	0.00	0.00
13	0.00	0.46	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00
16	0.00	0.42	0.00	0.00
17	0.00	0.00	0.65	0.00
18	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.00
19	0.00	0.00	0.69	0.00
20	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.00
21	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00
22	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.00
23	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.00
24	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00
25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.46
26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.23
27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16
28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.49
29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.34
30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24
31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13
32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07
33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.19
34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20
35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
36	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.00
37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
38	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.00
39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

4. Conclusions and future work

4.1. Conclusions

To sum up the results of the research, there is no clear best topology when it comes to ensuring the best possible performance while being as robust as possible to potential constraints encountered in edge-based infrastructures. However, depending on the specific character of the environment some helpful indications can be found.

For example, in case of the data distribution on client nodes varying significantly from the global data distribution, a simple centralized topology may be a worthy choice. A star architecture with ring-based groups, on the other hand, should be avoided if possible or mitigated using grouping principles listed in (Lee et al. 2020).

Alternatively, if the environment is stable and it's more important to maintain high model performance on edge than its accuracy on the whole dataset, a clustered architecture should be considered (with the added caveat of ensuring the appropriate number of clusters is selected).

In environments, in which the data distribution on client nodes is identical to the global data distribution with all certainty (or with possible additional grouping of the client nodes), the star architecture with ring-based groups seems like a safe alternative due to its fast convergence, high robustness to communication interruptions and user dropouts, as well as a lesser need for additional communication and computing resources than in the case of hierarchical architecture. Furthermore, for this topology, a bigger number of client nodes per group is preferred. Importantly, these environments do not allow for the efficient utilization of clustered topologies, due to the differences in local data distribution being too small to necessitate the simultaneous training of several machine learning models.

If, on the other hand, the data distribution on the client nodes may slightly differ from the global data distribution or there is a need to reduce the number of devices directly contacting the global server, but the requirement of additional communication between client and edge nodes can be easily fulfilled, a hierarchical topology is a potential solution. Additionally, a larger number of client nodes per edge node may be preferred in this situation.

4.2. Future work

As for the future work, the possible improvements and extensions to the current research are numerous. One particularly promising concerns the conduct of experiments on multiple machines instead of one, which would allow for more extensive constraint simulation as well as a bigger scale of experiments with many more nodes.

Furthermore, a more thorough investigation of node grouping as a possible way to mitigate some of the simulated constraints would be a valuable next step, starting with the algorithm described in (ibid.) is also a worthwhile idea.

Finally, a wider choice of machine learning models used in experiments, more thorough investigation of the influence of the difference between local and global data distribution on the final results, as well as the inclusion of examples representing more types of topology in Federated Systems are all worthwhile ideas to consider.

Bibliography

- Ahmed, Ejaz and Mubashir Husain Rehmani (2017). *Mobile edge computing: opportunities, solutions, and challenges*.
- Aledhari, Mohammed et al. (2020). “Federated Learning: A Survey on Enabling Technologies, Protocols, and Applications”. eng. In: *IEEE access* 8, pp. 140699–140725. ISSN: 2169-3536.
- An Industrial Grade Federated Learning Framework* (accessed in 2022). URL: <https://fate.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- Anjum, Asra and Shaik Apsar Pasha (2015). “A Brief View of Computer Network Topology for Data Communication and Networking”. eng. In: *International journal of engineering trends and technology* 22.7, pp. 319–324. ISSN: 2231-5381.
- Bao, Wei et al. (2017). “Follow me fog: Toward seamless handover timing schemes in a fog computing environment”. In: *IEEE Communications Magazine* 55.11, pp. 72–78.
- Basiri, Ali et al. (2016). “Chaos Engineering”. In: *IEEE Software* 33.3, pp. 35–41. DOI: 10.1109/MS.2016.60.
- Bellet, Aurélien, Anne-Marie Kermarrec, and Erick Lavoie (2021). “D-Cliques: Compensating NonIIDness in Decentralized Federated Learning with Topology”. In: *CoRR* abs/2104.07365. arXiv: 2104.07365. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.07365>.
- Beutel, Daniel J. et al. (2020). “Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Research Framework”. In: *CoRR* abs/2007.14390. arXiv: 2007.14390. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.14390>.
- Bilal, Kashif et al. (2018). “Potentials, trends, and prospects in edge technologies: Fog, cloudlet, mobile edge, and micro data centers”. In: *Computer Networks* 130, pp. 94–120. ISSN: 1389-1286. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2017.10.002>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128617303778>.
- Bouacida, Nader et al. (2020). “Adaptive Federated Dropout: Improving Communication Efficiency and Generalization for Federated Learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/2011.04050. arXiv: 2011.04050. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.04050>.
- Cao, Jie, Quan Zhang, and Weisong Shi (2018). “Challenges and Opportunities in Edge Computing”. In: *Edge Computing: A Primer*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 59–70.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ISBN: 978-3-030-02083-5. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-02083-5_5. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02083-5_5.
- Cao, Tien-Dung et al. (2020). “A Federated Learning Framework for Privacy-preserving and Parallel Training”. In: *CoRR* abs/2001.09782. arXiv: 2001.09782. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.09782>.
- Chen, Zhikun et al. (2021). *DACFL: Dynamic Average Consensus Based Federated Learning in Decentralized Topology*. arXiv: 2111.05505 [cs.LG].
- Chollet, Francois et al. (2015). *Keras*. URL: <https://github.com/fchollet/keras>.
- Chou, Li et al. (2021). “Efficient and Less Centralized Federated Learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/2106.06627. arXiv: 2106.06627. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.06627>.
- Daniel J.Beutel Taner Topal, Nicholas D.Lane Akhil Mathur Titouan Parcollet Xinchu Qiu (n.d.). *Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Framework reference manual*. URL: <https://flower.dev/docs/>.
- Ding, Yucheng et al. (2020). “Distributed Optimization over Block-Cyclic Data”. In: *CoRR* abs/2002.07454. arXiv: 2002.07454. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.07454>.
- Duan, Moming et al. (2021). “Self-Balancing Federated Learning With Global Imbalanced Data in Mobile Systems”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems* 32.1, pp. 59–71. DOI: 10.1109/TPDS.2020.3009406.
- Eichner, Hubert et al. (2019). “Semi-Cyclic Stochastic Gradient Descent”. In: *CoRR* abs/1904.10120. arXiv: 1904.10120. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1904.10120>.
- Ek, Sannara et al. (2021a). “A Federated Learning Aggregation Algorithm for Pervasive Computing: Evaluation and Comparison”. In: *CoRR* abs/2110.10223. arXiv: 2110.10223. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.10223>.
- (2021b). “A Federated Learning Aggregation Algorithm for Pervasive Computing: Evaluation and Comparison”. In: *CoRR* abs/2110.10223. arXiv: 2110.10223. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.10223>.
- Fulber-Garcia, Vinicius et al. (2020). “Network service topology: Formalization, taxonomy and the CUSTOM specification model”. In: *Computer Networks* 178, p. 107337. ISSN: 1389-1286. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107337>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1389128619312460>.
- Ghosh, Avishek et al. (2020). *An Efficient Framework for Clustered Federated Learning*. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2006.04088. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.04088>.
- Guo, Yan et al. (2020). “User allocation-aware edge cloud placement in mobile edge computing”. In: *Software, practice experience* 50.5, pp. 489–502. ISSN: 0038-0644.

- Hard, Andrew et al. (2018). “Federated Learning for Mobile Keyboard Prediction”. In: *CoRR* abs/1811.03604. arXiv: 1811.03604. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1811.03604>.
- Hong, Cheol-Ho and Blesson Varghese (2019). “Resource Management in Fog/Edge Computing: A Survey on Architectures, Infrastructure, and Algorithms”. eng. In: *ACM computing surveys* 52.5, pp. 1–37. ISSN: 0360-0300.
- Hu, Chenghao, Jingyan Jiang, and Zhi Wang (2019). “Decentralized Federated Learning: A Segmented Gossip Approach”. In: *CoRR* abs/1908.07782. arXiv: 1908.07782. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.07782>.
- Hu, Qinghao et al. (2021). “Characterization and Prediction of Deep Learning Workloads in Large-Scale GPU Datacenters”. In: *CoRR* abs/2109.01313. arXiv: 2109.01313. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.01313>.
- Jiang, Jingyan et al. (2020). “BACombo—Bandwidth-Aware Decentralized Federated Learning”. In: *Electronics* 9.3. ISSN: 2079-9292. DOI: 10.3390/electronics9030440. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/9/3/440>.
- Jing, Qinghe et al. (2019). “Quantifying the Performance of Federated Transfer Learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/1912.12795. arXiv: 1912.12795. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1912.12795>.
- Kamp, Michael, Jonas Fischer, and Jilles Vreeken (2021). “Federated Learning from Small Datasets”. In: *CoRR* abs/2110.03469. arXiv: 2110.03469. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.03469>.
- Khan, Latif U et al. (2020a). “Edge-Computing-Enabled Smart Cities: A Comprehensive Survey”. eng. In: *IEEE internet of things journal* 7.10, pp. 10200–10232. ISSN: 2327-4662.
- Khan, Latif U. et al. (2020b). “Federated Learning for Internet of Things: Recent Advances, Taxonomy, and Open Challenges”. In: *CoRR* abs/2009.13012. arXiv: 2009.13012. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.13012>.
- Khan, Wazir Zada et al. (2019). “Edge computing: A survey”. In: *Future Generation Computer Systems* 97, pp. 219–235. ISSN: 0167-739X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.02.050>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X18319903>.
- Konečný, Jakub, Brendan McMahan, and Daniel Ramage (2015). “Federated Optimization: Distributed Optimization Beyond the Datacenter”. In: *CoRR* abs/1511.03575. arXiv: 1511.03575. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1511.03575>.
- Krizhevsky, Alex (2009). *Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images*. Tech. rep.
- Kumar, Siddhartha et al. (2021). “Coding for Straggler Mitigation in Federated Learning”. eng. In.

- Ledenev, Alexei (2021). *Pumba: chaos testing tool for Docker*. Tech. rep. URL: <https://github.com/alexei-led/pumba>.
- Lee, Jin-Woo et al. (2020). “TornadoAggregate: Accurate and Scalable Federated Learning via the Ring-Based Architecture”. In: *CoRR* abs/2012.03214. arXiv: 2012.03214. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.03214>.
- Lee, Yunhyeok and Yi Liu (2022). “Using Refactoring to Migrate REST Applications to GRPC”. In: *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Southeast Conference*. ACM SE ’22. Virtual Event: Association for Computing Machinery, 219–223. ISBN: 9781450386975. DOI: 10.1145/3476883.3520220. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3476883.3520220>.
- Li, Yuzheng et al. (2021). “A Blockchain-Based Decentralized Federated Learning Framework with Committee Consensus”. In: *IEEE Network* 35.1, pp. 234–241. DOI: 10.1109/MNET.011.2000263.
- Liao, Haijun et al. (2020). “Learning-Based Context-Aware Resource Allocation for Edge Computing-Empowered Industrial IoT”. eng. In: *IEEE internet of things journal* 7.5, pp. 4260–4277. ISSN: 2327-4662.
- Liu, Peixi et al. (2022). *Vertical Federated Edge Learning with Distributed Integrated Sensing and Communication*. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2201.08512. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.08512>.
- Liu, Ruixuan et al. (2020). “FedSel: Federated SGD under Local Differential Privacy with Top-k Dimension Selection”. In: *CoRR* abs/2003.10637. arXiv: 2003.10637. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.10637>.
- Liu, Yang, Tianjian Chen, and Qiang Yang (2018). “Secure Federated Transfer Learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/1812.03337. arXiv: 1812.03337. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1812.03337>.
- Lu, Yunlong et al. (2020). “Blockchain and Federated Learning for Privacy-Preserved Data Sharing in Industrial IoT”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 16.6, pp. 4177–4186. DOI: 10.1109/TII.2019.2942190.
- Mastorakis, Spyridon et al. (2020). “ICedge: When Edge Computing Meets Information-Centric Networking”. eng. In: *IEEE internet of things journal* 7.5, pp. 4203–4217. ISSN: 2327-4662.
- McMahan, H. Brendan et al. (2016). “Federated Learning of Deep Networks using Model Averaging”. In: *CoRR* abs/1602.05629. arXiv: 1602.05629. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1602.05629>.
- Merkel, Dirk (2014). “Docker: lightweight linux containers for consistent development and deployment”. In: *Linux journal* 2014.239, p. 2.

- Mhaisen, Naram et al. (2022). “Optimal User-Edge Assignment in Hierarchical Federated Learning Based on Statistical Properties and Network Topology Constraints”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering* 9.1, pp. 55–66. DOI: 10.1109/TNSE.2021.3053588.
- Mothukuri, Virraji et al. (2021). “A survey on security and privacy of federated learning”. In: *Future Generation Computer Systems* 115, pp. 619–640. ISSN: 0167-739X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.10.007>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X20329848>.
- Murdoch, Blake (2021). “Privacy and artificial intelligence: Challenges for protecting health information in a new era”. In: *BMC Medical Ethics* 22.1. DOI: 10.1186/s12910-021-00687-3.
- Nguyen, Dinh C. et al. (2021). “Federated Learning for Internet of Things: A Comprehensive Survey”. In: *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials* 23.3, pp. 1622–1658. DOI: 10.1109/COMST.2021.3075439.
- Nilsson, Adrian et al. (2018). “A Performance Evaluation of Federated Learning Algorithms”. In: *Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Distributed Infrastructures for Deep Learning*. DIDL '18. Rennes, France: Association for Computing Machinery, 1–8. ISBN: 9781450361194. DOI: 10.1145/3286490.3286559. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3286490.3286559>.
- OpenMined (accessed in 2022). *PySyft*. URL: <https://blog.openmined.org/tag/pysyft/>.
- PaddleFL* (accessed in 2022). URL: <https://paddlefl.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>.
- Pappas, Christodoulos et al. (2021). “IPLS : A Framework for Decentralized Federated Learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/2101.01901. arXiv: 2101.01901. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.01901>.
- Phillippa Biggs John Garrity, Connie LaSalle (Cisco) Anna Polomska Dr.Robert Pepper (2015). “Harnessing the Internet of Things for Global Development”. eng. In: URL: <http://handle.itu.int/11.1002/pub/80d1ac90-en>.
- Powers, David (Jan. 2008). “Evaluation: From Precision, Recall and F-Factor to ROC, Informedness, Markedness Correlation”. In: *Mach. Learn. Technol.* 2.
- Qiu, Xinchu et al. (2021). “A first look into the carbon footprint of federated learning”. In: *CoRR* abs/2102.07627. arXiv: 2102.07627. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.07627>.
- Rahman, K. M. Jawadur et al. (2021). “Challenges, Applications and Design Aspects of Federated Learning: A Survey”. In: *IEEE Access* 9, pp. 124682–124700. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3111118.
- Ramírez, Sebastián (2021). *FastAPI Software, Version 0.70.1*. Tech. rep. Berlin, Germany. URL: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Reddi, Sashank J. et al. (2020). “Adaptive Federated Optimization”. In: *CoRR* abs/2003.00295. arXiv: 2003.00295. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.00295>.
- Rehman, Muhammad Habib ur et al. (Apr. 2021). “TrustFed: A Framework for Fair and Trustworthy Cross-Device Federated Learning in IIoT”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* PP. DOI: 10.1109/TII.2021.3075706.
- Ren, Ju et al. (2020). “A Survey on End-Edge-Cloud Orchestrated Network Computing Paradigms: Transparent Computing, Mobile Edge Computing, Fog Computing, and Cloudlet”. eng. In: *ACM computing surveys* 52.6, pp. 1–36. ISSN: 0360-0300.
- Roh, Yuji, Geon Heo, and Steven Euijong Whang (2021). “A Survey on Data Collection for Machine Learning: A Big Data - AI Integration Perspective”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 33.4, pp. 1328–1347. DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2019.2946162.
- Sasaki, Yutaka (Jan. 2007). “The truth of the F-measure”. In: *Teach Tutor Mater*.
- Shaukat, Usman et al. (2016). “Cloudlet deployment in local wireless networks: Motivation, architectures, applications, and open challenges”. In: *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 62, pp. 18–40.
- Skarlat, Olena et al. (2017). “Towards QoS-Aware Fog Service Placement”. In: *2017 IEEE 1st International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC)*, pp. 89–96. DOI: 10.1109/ICFEC.2017.12.
- Stallkamp, J. et al. (2012). “Man vs. computer: Benchmarking machine learning algorithms for traffic sign recognition”. In: *Neural Networks* 0, pp. –. ISSN: 0893-6080. DOI: 10.1016/j.neunet.2012.02.016. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0893608012000457>.
- Tak, Afaf and Soumaya Cherkaoui (2021). “Federated Edge Learning: Design Issues and Challenges”. In: *IEEE Network* 35.2, pp. 252–258. DOI: 10.1109/MNET.011.2000478.
- TensorFlow Federated: Machine Learning on Decentralized Data* (accessed in 2022). URL: <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated?hl=en>.
- Van Rossum, Guido (2020). *The Python Library Reference, release 3.8.2*. Python Software Foundation.
- Van Rossum, Guido and Fred L Drake Jr (1995). *Python reference manual*. Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica Amsterdam.
- Wei, Kang et al. (2022). *Vertical Federated Learning: Challenges, Methodologies and Experiments*. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2202.04309. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.04309>.

- Wortmann, Felix and Kristina Flüchter (2015). "Internet of Things: Technology and Value Added". eng. In: *Business information systems engineering* 57.3, pp. 221–224. ISSN: 2363-7005.
- Xia, Qi et al. (2021). "A survey of federated learning for edge computing: Research problems and solutions". In: *High-Confidence Computing* 1.1, p. 100008. ISSN: 2667-2952. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hcc.2021.100008>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S266729522100009X>.
- Yang, Qiang et al. (2019). "Federated Machine Learning: Concept and Applications". In: *CoRR* abs/1902.04885. arXiv: 1902.04885. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.04885>.
- Zheng, Huadi, Haibo Hu, and Ziyang Han (2020). "Preserving User Privacy for Machine Learning: Local Differential Privacy or Federated Machine Learning?" In: *IEEE Intelligent Systems* 35.4, pp. 5–14. DOI: 10.1109/MIS.2020.3010335.

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1. Appendix 1: Additional plots available on <https://github.com/Karolina-Bogacka/flTopologyThesis>